

OUTCOMES OF A GENDERED APPROACH IN INTEGRATED WATER RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

¹ANOUSHKA RAJ, ²NIMISHA SINGLA, ³ANUNAY A. GOUR

^{1,2,3}Department of Environmental Engineering, Delhi Technological University, Delhi, India
E-mail: ¹anoushkaraj_2k18en010@dtu.ac.in, ²nimishasingla_2k18en029@dtu.ac.in, ³anunaygour@dtu.ac.in

Abstract - This paper attempts to integrate social and engineering sciences in the context of water resource management. It evaluates the effectiveness of a robust prototype for tackling the prevailing water crisis. Our study identifies women as critical stakeholders through a close analysis of two cases from different parts of the world. It explores how getting women actively involved in IWRM strategies has led to significant desired results and often solved critical issues. An in-depth literature study was carried out to extract secondary data from reports, research papers, theses, and other publications on the feminist approaches to water management. The article analyzes how gender mainstreaming is an essential aspect of conversations about IWRM and highlights the main sectors as the intersection of genders, the importance of adopting a gendered approach, and how to extract the most out of these benefits.

Keywords - Dublin Principles, Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM), Gender Mainstreaming, Women, Water

I. INTRODUCTION

Water is an extraordinary substance. It is a commonly understood fact that becomes complex when water is viewed as a commodity for domestic, agricultural, industrial, maritime, and recreational purposes - observed through society's purview of culture, economics, law, and politics. Our history of failure to recognize the economic and ecological value of water has led to its fragmented indiscriminate use, which has become a significant challenge today (Mukhtarov 2008). Social sciences can no longer be separated from the search party finding solutions for environmental problems, especially water issues. This is because water issues are as complex as water, if not more.

Against the backdrop of climate change and manifold increase in water scarcity and pollution with a continuous seemingly never-ending ascend in needs (Global Water Partnership 2016), a systematic (but not homogenizing) approach to deal with these complexities is the need of the hour. Today's crisis is not about satisfying needs but about preventing poor management (World Water Council 2000). We have jeopardised the precious resource with bad governance, institutions, incentives and allocation (World Water Council 2000). Sustainable water management should accommodate all five components of sustainability: technical, social, financial, environmental, and institutional (Maharaj).

This is where the concept of Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) steps in. The ideas that make up the concept of IWRM have been around since the very first global water conference in Mar del Plata in 1977. However, IWRM was first formally debated upon during the Earth Summit in Rio in 1992, which defined it as '*a process which promotes the co-ordinated development and management of*

water, land and related resources, in order to maximize the resultant economic and social welfare in an equitable manner without compromising the sustainability of vital ecosystems.'

The Dublin Principles submitted in the Rio "Earth Summit" remain the standard for policy-making and deliberation of the issues encompassing utility, management, and conservation of water (Rahaman 2005), also known as Dublin - Rio principles (Global Water Partnership 1992), these are -

Principle 1 – Recognizing the importance of freshwater

Freshwater is a limited and vulnerable resource vital to sustaining life, maintaining the environment, and bringing about development.

Principle 2 – Recognizing the importance of stakeholder participation

Water development and management (including but not limited to deliberation and decision making) should be based on a participatory approach - involving users, planners, and policy-makers at all levels

Principle 3 – Recognizing gender mainstreaming

Women play a central part in the provision, management, and safeguarding of water.

Principle 4 – Recognizing water as an economic good

Water has an economic value in all its competing uses and should be recognized as an economic good.

Integrated Water Resources Management is a universal and all-inclusive approach to handling water problems. It is not a series of steps to be followed fixedly. The inherent philosophy of IWRM is that the process should be flexible - to be responsive to the changing requirements of a region and its people and to continue providing the solutions. It recognizes stakeholders other than the

traditional "water professionals". This approach tries to micromanage global water resources (especially freshwater ones) by considering the "watershed" as a unit. It directly challenges the conventional, free-willed, localized, and fractional management and development of water. It also involves layering and making sense of different reality perceptions as an engineer would see a river basin much differently than a farmer or an industrialist (Mostert 2008). This, however, cannot be achieved solely by technical considerations - in isolation of other aspects of human life (Global Water Partnership 2017).

IWRM is required to address the prevailing social and gendered disbalance of unequal access and control of resources, costs, benefits, and decision-making between women and men. This has been elucidated clearly in the third Dublin Principle, which is our main area of focus in this paper.

II. FOUR PILLARS OF IWRM AND GENDER MAINSTREAMING

For IWRM to be truly useful, it should be held up by the four crucial "pillars": *environmental sustainability, economic efficiency, social equity, and water governance*. (Jønch-Clausen 2001)

Arising around the same time as IWRM, gender mainstreaming is an essential aspect of policy-making. The first mention of gender mainstreaming was at the World Conference on Women held in Nairobi in 1985. (UNEP 1997) A decade later, the Fourth United Nations World Conference on Women in Beijing highlighted gender mainstreaming as an essential stepping stone in international gender equality policy. The Council of Europe was also set forth a definition of gender mainstreaming, claiming that it is '*the (re) organization, improvement, development, and evaluation of policy processes, so that a gender equality perspective is incorporated in all policies at all levels and all stages, by the actors normally involved in policy-making.*' (Council of Europe)

The development and design of policies, advocacy, administrative and legislative decisions, scientific research, resource distribution and management, execution of projects, monitoring of water schemes are all sectors where a gender perspective is required. (UN Women) As a concept, gender mainstreaming involves analyzing women and men's implications due to any planned action. This is done through legislation, policies, or programs, across all areas and tiers and in all political, economic, and societal spheres. Both communities are equally benefited, the prevalent inequality is not sustained, and gender equality is achieved ultimately. (Global Water Partnership 2016; Mehra 2006)

It is crucial to develop an understanding of what **gender mainstreaming in water management** means. Gender is something that we have, but gender

is also something that society imposes on us. The linkages between gender and the four pillars of IWRM are as follows:

2.1. Gender and Environmental Sustainability

Water is a vital component of nature and is required for the sustenance of life. The masses primarily use water to meet their social and economic needs. However, a much more prominent pollution source is industries. Those from the economically weaker strata, which has a higher percentage of women, are directly exposed to water sources with industrial pollution and hence suffer even more.

Climate change is also not gender-neutral (Women Watch 2016). It has been noted that environmental degradation is closely related to poverty and the varied accessibility of resources for men and women. (Morales 2007; Machado 1999) Women are never provided the strategies and resources to use in case of disasters and hence are the most severely impacted by flood, drought, cloudbursts, or the likes.

2.2. Gender and Economic Efficiency

Technology choice and affordability are interlinked. Considering the diverse needs of different genders results in a more accommodating, user-sensitive, and, ultimately, sustainable service. For example, community standpipes are sometimes preferred over taps by people from low-income backgrounds. (Dapaah 2017) Consultation thus becomes integral to provide solutions that would be accepted.

International corporations and national governments are not investing commensurately on public water services. It can be attributed to several factors, such as post-crisis restrictive political expenditure, falling tax revenues, and foreign aid. In the poorest households, especially in rural areas, the quality and quantity of drinking water are steadily declining due to the price hikes. A considerable amount of their income is spent on paying for water.

Considering past experiences and results, we can clearly state that economic crises have a gendered impact. (Morales 2007) The shortage in employment, stress on social welfare, income shocks, and austerity measures hit females the hardest, owing to how they are mostly occupied in unpaid and unrecognized domestic chores. (UNDP 2006) Even their working concentration is mainly confined to the informal economy sector (with lower earnings and less social protection). It ensures that they are in a weaker position to survive crises.

2.3. Gender and Social Equity

Despite a willingness to pay for improved water supplies from women's side, many schemes have failed owing to intrahousehold biases and patriarchal structures (Green 1995). Despite reforms, the

legislative groups in society are still dominated by males, which often leads to the systematic exploitation of resources on a large scale. Thus, groups that are not diverse have a higher potential to do damage.

A wide range of domestic errands requires water use, such as clothes washing, utensil washing, and even water collection. If water is supplied by any source that requires additional manual work, then it is usually collected by women and children who spend a large chunk of their time and energy fetching water. Women in Asia and Africa walk as much as 3.5 miles a day, carrying almost 5 gallons of water on their shoulders. (Khiyara 2016) Another issue that arises during economic crises is an increase in violence against women, which has primarily been attributed to the additional stress and pressure that families and communities are going through during these times. Lack of proper sanitation facilities has also led to an increased risk of rape. (Khiyara 2016)

Usually, the parley regarding women and water is limited to sanitation and domestic use (Green 1995) - domains that society directly and obviously relates them with. A lot of schools and public facilities in developing countries do not have access to washrooms, especially female toilets. Public defecation and urination not only pose health issues but also raise security concerns. Once women hit puberty, they are often seen being absent for long durations or even dropping out from schools (Barton) since there are no facilities that could help ease their menstruation (Khiyara 2016).

2.4. Gender and Water Governance

People who plan the water supply distribution systems have to look into industrial, agricultural, and domestic demands. Due to the lack of women in governance and deliberative positions, domiciliary needs are often considered less important, and the responsibility of finding sufficient water for everyday activities is borne by women. (Cleaver 2010)

Women employed in all sectors, be it primary, secondary, and tertiary, suffer from gender inequality during a financial crisis. (Bora 2012) Low food security puts the women, considered water providers and caregivers, under extreme pressure, and often jeopardizes their health. (Ruel, Marie T. et al 2017) Additionally, many secondary sectors prefer employing male candidates over female ones. Recent post-crisis budget cuts and fiscal stimulus packages also impact women the most, as already the present gap is not filled. (Liang, Y. 2014)

Irrigation schemes initiated by associations of water users see the involvement of the corresponding land title holders. These landowners are mostly men, which translates into female farmers not getting

represented in the decision making. It leaves them with less or no irrigation water according to their needs.

Inculcating IWRM and gender mainstreaming has led to improvements in the implementation of water policies around the world. The universal application of this juxtapositioning has led to the resolution of issues that seemed inherently unsolvable, two of which are studied as follows.

III. CASE STUDIES: POSITIVE OUTCOMES OF A GENDERED APPROACH

3.1. Malawi

Malawi is a small, landlocked country in Africa. It faces a continuous threat of water scarcity as it is one of the lowest per capita water availability countries in Africa (UNDP 2006).

In the 1990s, Malawi's government tried to deliver piped water to low-income households through a newly developed community management system. It involved the construction of over 600 Communal Water Points spread over 50 districts. To govern this system and collect the fee, "Tap Committees" were formed, which consisted almost completely of men. These men worked away from homes and were unable to curb the wastage, properly collect contributions from each household every month, and pay metered water bills on their behalf. Fee collection was erratic, and often aggressive strategies were employed needlessly (UNDP 2006). It made the entire plan economically unsustainable.

A gendered approach was then improvised and implemented. The responsibility of fee collection was shifted to women, making the entire process more punctual and less conflictive, while also fulfilling the dual purpose of cost recovery and financial security for around 24,000 low-income families (Maharaj). Several old problems, such as the mismanagement of money, lack of Tap committee meetings, changing water points by various groups, lack of attendance in leadership courses, and disagreements in the opening/closing time of taps, were amended. Hygiene and sanitation were significantly improved once the women stepped in.

Women were then taught various technical skills, and have now almost completely taken over the Tap Committees, handling technical, financial, and social aspects. Women make up over 90% of the committees and are the longest surviving active members. Due to their progressive work, water bills are paid regularly, timely and frequent meetings are a norm, membership of the water points has increased, and user satisfaction levels are higher than ever. Men have been taught to develop a more positive attitude toward women's involvement, and lately, women

have also begun redesigning the water points to make them more convenient.

3.2. Pakistan

Under the exemplary individual leadership of Nasim Bibi, Banda Golra, a hamlet in Pakistan with just over a hundred houses, could get its water supply scheme. Earlier, the villagers accessed water from only two natural springs, which they shared with livestock and wildlife. There was one communal government pipeline, through which water ran twice a week. It was not sufficient for the residents. The domestic setting of traditional gender roles in the small village meant large families, high illiteracy rates among women, and little sharing of the decision making power. There was a severe case of diarrhea amongst the children.

The community-based organization (CBO) formed under Nasim Bibi in 2002 was eligible to receive support from a regional NGO, Sarhad Rural Support Programme (SRSP), which lent out money to CBOs. The project to tackle the decades-old water access problem involved installing seven new hand pumps in different locations in the village. The community bore 20 percent and SRSP 80 percent of the costs. Strategy formulation and implementation by women led to the group's success in bringing water to the village. (United Nations 2006)

Among the many positive outcomes of this effort, the ones most noteworthy are sanitation and women empowerment. With an increased water supply in households, the time needed for fetching water significantly decreased, and the bathing frequency, especially for girls and women, increased. A sense of ownership and security regarding the cleanliness of water resources was instilled. An open discussion regarding health issues is now possible in the community. Conscious efforts by women to include men in the discourse around their endeavors proved rewarding. Their decision-making power has increased, and they now found a willing audience in their generally oppressive households (Mayanja 2006).

3.3. Commonalities

The case studies put the spotlight on women with a focus on the world's water resources that have been traditionally exploited and, like nature, considered inferior to technological advancement (Agarwal 1992).

A close study of the gender-centric IWRM solutions in Malawi and Pakistan indicate the benefits of involving women in managing our water resources. It gives females their due say in the decision making processes that impact them and their families. By eradicating the need for fetching water and other banal tasks, these methods free up their time for more social and income-generating activities. (Mehra 2006;

Barton) Involving women in simple governing and financial tasks have led to a marked improvement in the health of the entire community, all of whom now have access to cleaner water. What has changed is not the source, or the system of water supply, but just the gender of the leaders at the helm of the management systems.

With an essential natural resource coming under their direct governance, women in these schemes have become more economically independent and financially literate. In both situations, the switch of responsibility has led to improved sanitation. As seen in Malawi and Pakistan, this has also helped blur traditional gender roles and broader acceptance of women outside their domestic tasks. The switch has markedly improved the spirit of the community and ownership to less aggressive practices. With women spearheading new projects, handling fee payments, and keeping a check on security and technical issues, natural water resources are being used more responsibly and consciously. It has resulted in better water for all community members, with much lesser wastage and proper distribution of power.

IV. CONCLUSION

In 2006, The Economist proclaimed that women are "the world's most underutilized resource." This paper looks into how gender mainstreaming is a key component in fully realizing IWRM. It has drawn relations between two case studies and looked into the actual work being carried out to achieve one common end goal.

We are met with uncertainties at every step of IWRM. In addressing issues related to girls and women, it is imperative to ensure that their safety and rights are not compromised. Assessing how women and men manage water differently gives us access to study how to use water more efficiently and sustainably. By enabling effective use of financial instruments and national policies to protect the most vulnerable groups from suffering disproportionately, we can share benefits in an unbiased way. In the process we also protect the physical and psychological integrity of all groups.

In the spirit of Dublin principle 2, real participation has to go beyond mere consultancy - just like we have observed in the case studies. However, making projects people-centric doesn't necessarily mean that they are gender-sensitive. While addressing sanitation is a good start, it cannot continue to persist as the only way women are involved consciously in IWRM processes. Through successful establishment and management of gender-sensitive (or even women-centric) water supply project reports from across the world, it has been recurrently observed that women become more confident and self-reliant as they

improve their financial status, communication skills and leadership qualities. Another sanguine takeaway is of the ripple effect of men becoming more accepting of women in supervisory and decision making roles. Thus improving water-related issues improves women's quality of life in multiple ways and proves to be a positive externality for the society as a whole.

IWRM works on the tacit understanding that we are all "learning by doing". Efforts to share success stories with the rest of the world for drawing inspiration and asking for improvements will not only encourage meaningful dialogue but also a sense of a global community. We acknowledge that gender mainstreaming in IWRM in itself will not lead to the desired results, but it is unlikely that the goals can be achieved without it.

REFERENCES

- [1] Mukhtarov FG (2008) Intellectual history and current status of Integrated Water Resources Management: A global perspective. *Adaptive and Integrated Water Management*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp 167–185
- [2] Global Water Partnership (2016), "Gender practice in water governance programmes from design to results", available at: [www.gwp.org/Global/ToolBox/References/Gender%20Practice%20in%20Water%20Governance%20Programmes%20\(WGF,%202014\).pdf](http://www.gwp.org/Global/ToolBox/References/Gender%20Practice%20in%20Water%20Governance%20Programmes%20(WGF,%202014).pdf) (accessed September 20, 2016).
- [3] World Water Council. 2000. *World Water Vision: Making Water Everybody's business*. London: Earthscan
- [4] Niala Maharaj, Kusum Athukorala, Mariela Garcia Vargas, Gabriella Richardson. *Mainstreaming Gender in Water Resources Management Why and How*. Background paper for World Vision Process. Available at: https://sswm.info/sites/default/files/reference_attachments/MAHARAJ%201999%20Mainstreaming%20Gender%20in%20Water%20Resource%20Management.pdf
- [5] Rahaman MM, Varis O (2005) Integrated water resources management: evolution, prospects and future challenges. *Sustainability: Science, Practice and Policy* 1(1):15–21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15487733.2005.11907961>
- [6] Global Water Partnership (1992). *Dublin-Rio Principles*. <https://www.gwp.org/contentassets/05190d0c938f47d1b254d6606ec6bb04/dublin-rio-principles.pdf>
- [7] Mostert E, Craps M, Pahl-Wostl C (2008) Social learning: the key to integrated water resources management? *Water International* 33(3):293–304. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508060802275757>
- [8] Global Water Partnership (2017) <https://www.gwp.org/en/GWP-CEE/about/how/Vision-and-Mission/>
- [9] Jönch-Clausen T, Fugl J (2001) Firming up the Conceptual Basis of Integrated Water Resources Management. *International Journal of Water Resources Development* 17(4):501–510. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07900620120094055>
- [10] UNEP, (1997), *The fair share water strategy for sustainable development in Africa*. UNEP, Nairobi
- [11] Council of Europe. What is gender mainstreaming?. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/genderequality/what-is-gender-mainstreaming>
- [12] UN Women. Gender Mainstreaming. <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/osagi/gendermainstreaming.htm>
- [13] Mehra, R. and Gupta, G. (2006), "Gender mainstreaming: making it happen", available at: www.icrw.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/Gender-Mainstreaming-Making-It-Happen.pdf (accessed June 18, 2016).
- [14] Women Watch (2016), "Women, gender equality and climate change", available at: https://www.un.org/womenwatch/feature/climate_change/ (accessed June 16, 2016).
- [15] Moraes A, Perkins PE (2007) Women, Equity and Participatory Water Management in Brazil. *International Feminist Journal of Politics* 9(4):485–493. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616740701607986>
- [16] Machado, M., Benitez, M. and Rojas, M.H. (1999), "El Salvador: gender and environmental management", available at: http://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/PNACM528.pdf (accessed August 2, 2020).
- [17] UNDP (2006) *Resource Guide: Mainstreaming Gender in Water Management*.
- [18] Green C, Baden S (1995) *Integrated Water Resources Management: A Gender Perspective*. *IDS Bulletin* 26(1): 92–100. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1759-5436.1995.mp26001013.x>
- [19] Barton A. *Water in Crisis- Women in India*. The Water Project. <https://thewaterproject.org/water-crisis/water-in-crisis-india-women>
- [20] Khiyara, S. (2016), "Why is the global water crisis a women's issue and the top global risk over the next A decade?", available at: www.huffingtonpost.com/shailkhiyara/why-the-global-water-cris_b_12450260.html (accessed August 3, 2020).
- [21] Cleaver, F. and Hamada, K. (2010), "Good' water governance and gender equity: a troubled relationship", *Gender and Development*, Vol. 18 No. 1, pp. 27–41.
- [22] United Nations (2006) *Gender, Water, and Sanitation; Case Studies on Best Practices*. https://www.un.org/esa/sustdev/sdissues/water/casestudies_bestpractices.pdf
- [23] Mayanja, Rachel. (2006). *GENDER, WATER AND SANITATION CASE STUDIES ON BEST PRACTICES*. Available at: https://www.un.org/esa/sustdev/sdissues/water/casestudies_bestpractices.pdf
- [24] Agarwal B (1992) *The Gender and Environment Debate: Lessons from India In: Population and Environment*, 1st edn. Taylor & Francis.
- [25] Youn, B., 2012. *The Impact of Economic Crisis on Global Gender Inequality: An Empirical Analysis*. [online]
- [26] Ruel, M. T., Garrett, J., Yosef, S., & Olivier, M. (2017). *Urbanization, food security and nutrition. Nutrition and Health in a Developing World*, 705–735.
- [27] Liang, Y., & Hsu, S. (2014). Impacts of financial crisis and post-crisis policies on China: A gendered analysis. In *Gender Perspectives and Gender Impacts of the Global Economic Crisis* (pp. 132–156). Routledge.
- [28] Dapaah, Elizabeth K.; Harris, Leila M. (2017). *Framing community entitlements to water in Accra, Ghana: A complex reality*. *Geoforum*, 82(), 26–39. doi:10.1016/j.geoforum.2017.03.011

